

PRELIMINARY EVALUATION OF THE BIF AND MARBLE DEPOSITS OF THE AREA SOUTH OF MURO KASA, NORTHCENTRAL NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Geological mapping of the western part of Katakwa sheet 228NE in Toto Local Government of Nassarawa State has been done. Major rock units in the area are quartzites, marble, phyllite, mica, schist and banded iron formation(BIF). Structures identified include; foliations, joints, faults, folds and microfolds. The tonnage of the BIF and marble deposits in the study area is estimated to be 111,352,210 tons and 337,529,422 tons respectively. The BIF which occur as elongate bodies on the Muro hills is suitable for steel making while the marble which is calcitic can be used as chief components in the lime and calcium industries. The need to have a detailed geological study of the area is therefore suggested.

KEYWORDS: BIF, Marble, tonnage, deposit, Muro Kasa

INTRODUCTION

Muro Kasa lies approximately 11 km south of Gadabuke in Toto Local Government of Nassarawa between longitudes 7°15'00"E and 7°16'55"E and latitudes 8°18'51"N and 8°20'36"N. The study area covers about 12.25 square kilometer of the western part of Katakwa sheet 228NE. Gadabuke is accessible from the Nassarawa-Toto road through the Muro Kasa and Muro village(Fig.1). An ENE flowing Suwosadu stream in the north and a SSE flowing Tarka stream in the south and their tributaries drain the area. The geology of the area is defined by the Proterozoic metasediments(Fig.2). McCurry (1979) posits that the Toto area sediments were deposited between 1000 and 800 million years ago.

In the field, the lithologic units are closely associated, but particular attention was paid to the marble and banded iron formation because of their economic importance.

Marble

This rock type occupies a large portion of the study area stretching from Muro Kasa and occurs as an elongate body jutting out at the foot of the eastern slopes of the Muro hills. In the eastern section, the marble body is associated with the schist and some quartzites while the one in the south has sharp contact with the BIF. The bodies trend southwards beyond the study area.

Two types of marble are recognized in the study area. The first type has alternating bands of grey and white while the second is grey and sometimes greenish in colour. The two varieties are found occurring together especially along the stream channels. The general strike of the marble is N-S and the dip is approximately 70°W. Although boundaries were obscured by soil cover, the Suwosadu and Tarka stream channels were useful in tracing outcrop trends.

Fig. 1: Location Map of Study Area in Muro Kasa

Fig.2. Simplified Geological Map of Nigeria; 10 = Toto Schist Belt (After Ajibade, *et al* 1986)

Fig.3. Surface Sketch of the two BIF Bodies West of Muro

Fig .4. Surface Sketch of (A) Marble in contact with BIF and (B) Large Marble Body South of Muro

Banded Iron Formation

Banded Iron Formation outcrop in two bands in the northern section of the study area striking approximately in the N-S direction (Fig. 3). The western arm is approximately 120m wide and occupies about 3.5% of the study area while the eastern arm, which occupies about 5% of the study area varies in the width at different points along its length between 170 and 230m. The eastern body is somewhat displaced to about 100m by a fault line. The bodies are characterized by regular alternating thin layers of iron and quartzites.

Their contact with schist and marble is sharp. Generally, the iron ore layer varies in thickness from 5 to 10 mm while the quartz rich layers are less than 10mm thick. The bands are regular and parallel but occasionally, the quartz bands are white, brown to pale-grey coloured and alternate with dark iron ore rich bands consisting of iron-oxides, usually some silica. Gangue minerals associated with the iron ores include quartz, zircon and apatite (Aga, 2000).

Evaluation of both the BIF and marble bodies were carried out to access the potentials of the huge deposits.

METHODOLOGY

Estimation of BIF and Marble Reserves

The vertical thickness of the BIF estimated from contours is averagely 30m. Measurements on sections within boreholes on the marble around Muro Kasa indicate that the thickness varies from 29.70 to 33.05m. The specific gravity of the BIF is 3.60g/cm³ and the densities of the marble range between 2.49 and 3.17g/cm³.

Estimation of the Muro Kasa BIF reserves was done using the block method. The planar surface on the map of the two BIF bodies were subdivided into blocks of regular geometric form T₁, T₂, ...T₁₁ (Fig.3) and the volume of each block calculated.

Blocks T₁, T₅, T₇, T₈, T₁₀ and T₁₁ are trapeziums and have surface areas 59, 150m², 44,500m², 39,600m², 104,250m², 105,600m² and 201,250m² respectively. Blocks T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₆ are rectangular and have surface areas 81,400m², 114,000m², 71,000m² and 209,000m² respectively. Block T₆ is a semi-circle and has an area of 1,289m².

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total volume of the BIF bodies} &= \text{Total surface area} \times \text{average depth} \\ &= 1,031,039\text{m}^2 \times 30\text{m} \\ &= 30,931,170\text{m}^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total mass of BIF bodies} &= \text{Total volume} \times \text{mean density} \\ &= 30,931,170 \times 3.6 \times 10^3 \\ &= 1.1135221 \times 10^{11} \text{ kg.} \\ &= 111,352,210 \text{ tons of BIF} \end{aligned}$$

The same block method was employed to estimate the reserve of the marble bodies. The planar surface of the marble bodies was divided into blocks of regular geometric forms A₁, A₂,...A₆(Fig. 4).

Area of blocks A₂, A₄ and A₅ which are trapeziums are 171,000m², 1,210,000m², and 1,018,500m² respectively. Block A₁ is a semi-circle while A₃ is a rectangle with areas of 45,402m² and 253,000m² respectively. A₆ is a trapezium less blocks S¹ and S², with an area of 1,101,453m².

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total volume of the marble bodies} &= \text{Total surface area} \times \text{average depth} \\ &= 3,798,355\text{m}^2 \times 31.4\text{m} \\ &= 119,268,347 \text{ m}^3. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total mass of marble body} &= \text{Total volume of marble} \times \text{mean density of the marble} \\ &= 119,268,347 \times 2.83 \times 10^3 \\ &= 3.3753 \times 10^{11} \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

= 337,529,422 tons.

From the calculation, the total tonnage of the BIF and marble deposits in the study area sums up to 11,352,210 tons and 337,529,422 tons respectively. This overall tonnage calculation was however restricted to 30.0m and 31.4m depth range for BIF and marble deposit respectively. This estimate could however be surpassed as considerable quantities occur beyond this depth range. Larger scale mapping such as on 1:4,000 or 1:1000 would increase the accuracy of the tonnage value obtained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical Composition

Evaluation of mineral deposits such as BIF and marble in terms of its usage is largely dependent upon chemical analyses which were carried out by Anike, *et al* (1990) and Tegure (1989) respectively. These data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The result for BIF in Table 1 indicates that the Fe (29.59-36.72%), FeO (33.57-42.72%) and Fe₂O₃ (3.77-5.85%). This portrays a high magnetite content of the ores. SiO₂ content is between 43.12 and 43.12%, CaO accounts for 2.42 to 5.56% and MgO ranges from traces to 3.62%. Each of the other oxides: Al₂O₃, TiO₂, MnO and P₂O₅ have values less than 0.5%, sulphur content is 0.11-0.21% and the LOI averages 0.5%.

Table 1: Chemical Analysis of Banded Iron Formation (BIF) from Muro Hill (After Anike, *et al* 1990)

Oxides	Samples					
	TM-1A	TM-2A	TM-3A	TM-4A	TM-6A	TM-7A
SiO ₂	55.78	54.73	51.31	43.12	53.12	49.46
TiO ₂	0.10	0.08	0.11	0.22	0.22	0.24
Al ₂ O ₃	0.11	0.26	0.53	1.41	0.11	0.48
Fe ₂ O ₃	5.28	5.76	4.72	4.99	3.77	5.85
FeO	34.16	33.57	35.52	42.75	34.67	34.08
MnO	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.49	0.06	0.04
MgO	Tr	1.42	2.02	2.02	1.41	3.62
CaO	2.42	3.22	3.85	3.10	5.56	3.64
P ₂ O ₅	0.27	0.22	0.37	0.24	0.17	0.23
S	0.16	0.19	0.20	0.15	0.21	0.11
LOI	0.40	Nd	0.81	0.11	0.76	Nd
Total	98.74	99.49	99.47	98.60	100.06	97.75
Fe	30.23	30.12	30.91	36.72	29.59	30.58
Fe ²⁺ /Fe ³⁺	0.14	0.15	0.12	0.11	0.10	0.15

Table2: Chemical Analysis of Muro Kasa Marble (After Tegure, 1989)

Oxides	Samples					
	1	5A	12	5B	13	
SiO ₂	1.20	1.03	1.05	0.48	0.14	
CaO	39.66	44.27	46.64	47.39	42.95	
MgO	3.92	4.07	3.53	4.32	1.96	
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.80	2.13	0.80	1.60	1.92	
FeO	0.56	1.92	0.56	1.12	1.34	
MnO	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	
TiO ₂	0.03	0.02	Nd	Nd	Nd	
P ₂ O ₅	Tr	Tr	Tr	Tr	Tr	
Al ₂ O ₃	8.51	1.64	3.28	1.50	6.54	
Na ₂ O	0.67	0.36	1.48	0.31	0.83	
K ₂ O	0.29	0.19	0.79	0.19	0.19	
LOI	43.71	43.39	43.27	43.03	43.46	

From table 2, the marble contains 39.66% CaO, 1.5 to 8.51% Al₂O₃, SiO₂(0.48-1.3%), an average of 3.56% MgO and high LOI value of 43.71%. The high LOI value is probably due to the CO₂ content.

The Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ ratio ranges from 0.10 to 0.15 and the Mn²⁺/Fe total ratio varies from 0.00 to 0.01. The phosphorus content (0.17-0.37%) compares favourably with other known iron ores. For example, phosphorus content of the Itakpe hill iron deposit is 0.87-0.92% and Agbaja ironstone ores has 1.3-1.8 % P₂O₅. On the basis of this data, the iron ores in Toto area can also be used for steel making.

The investigated marble is calcitic (Aga, 2000) and about 94% pure, hence would be very useful in lime production. Lime is essential material in construction, manufacturing and chemical industries, especially in the production of plaster and alkali chemical (Tegure, 1989). The calcitic nature of the marble makes it suitable for the production of ferrous metallurgical flux. Other possible uses of the marble include terrazzo flooring, toothpaste and animal feed production; glass making, road aggregates and decorative materials manufacture.

CONCLUSION

Banded Iron Formation (BIF) and marble deposits occur associated with the Proterozoic low grade schist belts of the basement complex of Northwestern Nigeria. The presence of 111,352,210 tons and 337,529,422 tons of the BIF and marble were estimated. They both have a wide potential of utilization. In spite of the wide spread occurrence of these deposits, they have not received the attention they deserve as potential national reserves.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author wish to thank Dr. E. E. Ntekim of Federal University of Technology, Yola and Dr. E. C. Ashano of the University of Jos for their constructive criticism.

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Received for Publication: 10/07/2008

Accepted for Publication: 02/09/2008